

Report for the Robotics and AI Summer School 2022

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Purpose:

The purpose of this report is to organize the observations and the experiences that I had with the Robotics and AI Summer School 2022 which was carried out by IRI from the UPC.

Overview:

The Summer School was an online event that was carried out from the 4th to the 6th of July 2022. The following is information that was gathered from the website for Robotics and AI Summer School 2022.

Objective:

“The main objective of the Robotics and Artificial Intelligence Summer School 2022 is to disseminate robotic knowledge and experimentation to the technological community. Three days with an intensive agenda in current main robotic issues will be presented: Deep learning perception on Robotics, Human Robot Interaction and robot navigation and Assistive Robotics. The Summer School will include experimentation sessions.”

Intended audience:

“Students, master students, PhD researchers, Industry and Academia practitioners.”

Requirements/software:

“PC + Ubuntu 18.04 + ROS Melodic”

The link/url for the website for more information:

<https://www.iri.upc.edu/workshops/RoboticsAISummerSchool2022/>

Topics that Interested Me:

The following thoughts are on three of the presentations that piqued my interest the most. In the future I would like to learn about and/or involve myself in these fields.

1. *Intention, Prediction and Adaptation in Human-Robot Interaction and Collaboration*

Presentation done by Alberto Sanfeliu

This was the first presentation done in the Summer School. This topic has a lot to do with what interested me to come to Sanfeliu's lab in the first place. Finding a way to integrate robots with people safely and efficiently is a challenge that is currently being faced by researchers.

The field of AI was mentioned as one of the driving factors in developing intelligent robots. Decision making while taking in factors that are taken in by sensors for a robot is a challenge that AI can take on.

2. *Engineering Humanoid Robots for 24/7 Personal Assistance*

Presentation done by Tamim Asfour

Asfour's team at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology are at the cutting edge of creating helper humanoid robots. Humanoid robots are usually what people think of when they think of the word robots. In this case, they are becoming a reality and their applications in personal assistance have a wide range.

The way that the team working on these humanoid robots utilize deep episodic memory to encode experiences is a clever yet complex solution to creating a fully autonomous helper robot. Also, the manner in which they gather data of human movement for the data is fascinating. Using multiple sensors to record data of humans completing bimanual manipulation, the team was able to create an extensive dataset that could be used to develop these humanoid robots.

3. *Robot Motion Learning*

Presentation done by Adrià Colomé

Robot motion learning is definitely a topic in which a lot of expertise and prior experience is needed. Learning from Colomé and seeing an overview of the project got me interested in this field and its applications.

The approach used for reinforcement learning along with its formulas and theories was presented. Equally as impressive was the way the problem of robot motion learning was broken down using techniques that were referred to as dimensionality reduction. Overall, the example that was given of cloth manipulation was a great lens into how this sub-field of robotics is being advanced.

Conclusion:

The Robotics and AI Summer School was a great experience and served its purpose well. Information on the current state of robotics was disseminated well and for me, new interests piqued. It has inspired me to delve more into the world of robotics and AI in the future and truly made me realize how much knowledge and work is out there.

The participants all had interesting backgrounds, projects, and interests and it was nice to get to meet a few of them during the networking sessions. I consider it a success of the Summer School to get all these academics, engineers, and computer scientists together to discuss robotics and its development for the future.